

STUDIES IN KOLHAPUR FRESH-WATER FISHES

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Distribution of nitrogen in the crude proteins in the three varieties of fish (*vanz*, *kanas* and *kankut*) has been determined. Distribution of sulphur as total sulphur, cystine sulphur and methionine sulphur has also been determined.

In a previous communication (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1950, 38, 169) the author reported as follows the crude protein contents of these three varieties of fish found in the *Panchaganga* river near Kolhapur :

Fish.	Scientific name.	Crude protein in dried material.
<i>Vanz</i>	<i>Cirrhinus reba</i> (Ham.)	70.00%
<i>Kanas</i>	<i>Labeo calabasu</i> (Ham.)	68.44
<i>Kankut</i>	...	60.18

The present investigation relates to the distribution of nitrogen in these crude proteins, determined according to the method of van Slyke (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1911, 9, 185) as modified by Plimmer and Rosedale (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 1015) and by Cavett (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1932, 95, 335).

The amino-acid contents of sardine were determined by chemical methods by Dunn (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1926, 70, 697). Sekima and Akiyama (*J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1926, 32, 346) published the results of similar type of work on common fishes found along the Pacific coast; Rosedale (*Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 161) followed up by work on fishes available in the Singapore market. Basu and De (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1938, 26, 177) appear to be the first in India to have undertaken this type of work on Indian fishes—the fishes from Bengal.

The distribution of sulphur, in the present investigation, was ascertained by the estimation of total sulphur using peroxide bomb (Parr, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1909, 1, 689), their cystine sulphur according to the specific method of Callan and Toennies (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1941, 13, 450) and methionine-sulphur, according to that of Horn, Jones and Blum (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1946, 166, 313). These findings are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Fish.	Total sulphur.	Cystine sulphur.	Methionine sulphur.
<i>Vanz</i>	2.418%	1.619%	0.4072%
<i>Kanas</i>	2.343	1.412	0.5450
<i>Kankut</i>	2.452	1.659	0.5235

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of Sample.—The fresh fish was carefully skinned, and the edible portion of the flesh from the back near the middle of the body was cut out into very small pieces, and dried on a boiling water-bath, and then powdered. This powder was sieved through 1 mm. mesh, and freed from fat by extracting it with ether. It was then subjected to the various processes for the estimation of sulphur and of nitrogen. Total sulphur was estimated by using Parr's peroxide bomb.

TABLE II

Fish.	Crude protein.	BaSO ₄ .	Sulphur.
<i>Vanz</i>	0.200 g.	0.0352 g.	2.418%
<i>Kanas</i>	0.200	0.0341	2.343
<i>Kankut</i>	0.200	0.0357	2.452

Cystine Sulphur.—In each case 1 g. of protein and 10 g. of potassium permanganate were added to sodium hydroxide solution (6.4 g. in 150 c.c. water). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 48 hours, and the excess of permanganate removed with methyl alcohol. Then after acidifying the mixture, the insoluble portion was filtered off and the filtrate employed for the estimation of sulphur as barium sulphate in the usual manner.

TABLE III

Fish.	BaSO ₄ .	Sulphur.
<i>Vanz</i>	0.1178 g.	1.619%
<i>Kanas</i>	0.1028	1.412
<i>Kankut</i>	0.1208	1.659

Methionine Sulphur.—An accurately weighed amount of crude protein was refluxed on a sand-bath with 15 c.c. of 20% hydrochloric acid for 18 hours and then the hydrolysate was concentrated to nearly 5 c.c. and treated with a small quantity of vegetable charcoal, filtered, and made up to 100 c.c. Fifty c.c. of this were concentrated down to less than one fifth of its volume, and then after filtration, made exactly to 10 c.c. Two c.c. of this were taken for each colorimetric estimation, using Duboscq colorimeter. For purposes of comparison, an authentic sample of methionine was obtained from the B. D. H. A "blank" was run, which developed no colour. The readings obtained are as shown below.

TABLE IV

Fish.	Amount taken.	Colorimetric readings		Calculated amount of methionine in the total sample.	Percent.
		Unknown.	Standard.		
<i>Vanz</i>	0.6 g.	35	20	0.01138 g.	1.896%
		26.5	15		
		42.2	24		
<i>Kanas</i>	..	12.5	16.5	0.01517	2.5283
		16	21.2		
		21	27.5		
<i>Kankut</i>	..	21.8	16	0.01463	2.4383
		24.8	18		
		27.2	20		

Two c.c. of the "standard" taken for comparison contained 0.002 g. of methionine.

Distribution of Nitrogen.—The crude protein (6 g.) was hydrolysed with 100 c.c. of 25% hydrochloric acid on a sand-bath for 36 hours. The details of treatment were similar to those described by Plimmer and Rosedale (*loc. cit.*).

The estimation of nitrogen was carried out according to the Kjeldahl method as modified by Shedd (*J. Assoc. Off. Agr. Chem.*, 1927, 10, 50). The results are tabulated below indicating the nitrogen distribution in the crude proteins of these three varieties of fish.

TABLE V
Nitrogen calculated at 16% nitrogen (percent)

	<i>Vanz.</i>	<i>Kanas.</i>	<i>Kankut.</i>
Amide	0.333	0.333	0.422
Humin	1.2505	1.119	1.125
Diamino fraction.			
Arginine	12.775	11.169	12.891
Amino	19.325	16.700	21.287
Non-amino	17.662	10.160	13.544
Hystidine	0.706	2.680	4.700
Cystine	4.424	3.85 ^o	4.535
Lysine	19.076	9.151	12.665
Monoamino fraction.			
Amino	37.900	35.754	37.070
Non-amino	4.320	3.197	1.900
Total	80.7845	67.263	75.308

In all these samples the proportion of cystine appears to be very high. But previously the author and his co-workers (*J. Ind. Med. Res.*, 1950, 38, 259) had found a similar instance in *Shivada* (*Wallagonia attu*, Bloch) as against *Maral* (*Ophicephalus leucopunctatus*, Sykes) where it was only 2.85%. Histidine contents of *Vanz* appear to be comparatively very low. Of the three varieties, *Vanz* is the most popular in the local market.

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